

Estimating M4 Petal Modes in SCAO: Beyond Atmospheric Turbulence

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) modules such as the one of ArmazoNes high Dispersion Echelle Spectrograph (ANDES) instrument for the ESO Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), the presence of differential piston errors, so-called petal modes, between the six segments of the M4 deformable mirror represents a significant challenge. Unlike atmospheric turbulence, which produces smooth and continuous wavefronts, petal-like aberrations introduce sharp phase discontinuities that cannot be effectively captured by standard phase reconstruction techniques. A naive approach based on averaging the phase over each segment leads to incorrect estimation, as it primarily reflects atmospheric components, such as low-order modes like tilt and trefoil, which can significantly alter the segment-averaged phase without involving any actual inter-segment discontinuity. In this work, we explore and compare three alternative methods aimed at isolating and estimating the petal mode content from reconstructed wavefront phases. The first is a minimum mean square error (MMSE) estimator specifically designed to minimize cross-contamination from atmospheric modes. The second employs a first-derivative-based filter that is blind to edge discontinuities across segment boundaries. The third is a data-driven method based on machine learning, using a neural network trained to recognize petal patterns under various conditions. We present the problem framework and the specifics of each approach, along with simulation results that compare their accuracy, robustness, and sensitivity under realistic observing conditions. This work provides insight into possible strategies for petal mode control in SCAO systems, with direct impact on the stability and performance of ELT adaptive optics.

Keywords: Adaptive Optics, ELT, Petal Modes, Differential Piston, SCAO, Wavefront Control, Neural Networks

1. INTRODUCTION

In adaptive optics systems that incorporate a segmented deformable mirror (DM), such as the M4[11] of the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT[4]) or the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT[5, 3]), the introduction of differential piston aberrations can frequently occur. These specific aberrations are commonly referred to as petal modes or petals. A fundamental issue arises because these petals are not orthogonal to standard continuous modes, such as Zernikes or Karhunen-Loève (KL) modes, which are defined over the entire pupil. Consequently, determining the exact amount of "pure" petal aberration (that is, the petal aberration that is not intrinsically present in a continuous Von Karman turbulent phase—within the DM commands) is highly challenging.

The M4 adaptive mirror of the ELT has a diameter of 2.387 m and is composed of six petals arranged in a ring, controlled by roughly 5000 voice-coil actuators[11]. Its segmented geometry is a direct consequence of the spider structure supporting the M2 secondary mirror, whose six vanes divide the pupil into six sectors. This mechanical design is the root cause of the petal mode problem: each petal can accumulate a differential piston

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with respect to its neighbors that is not sensed by most standard wavefront sensing techniques, in particular those based on a Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor, which is blind to phase steps across segment boundaries[1]. The ArmazoNes high Dispersion Echelle Spectrograph (ANDES[7]), one of the first-light instruments of the ELT, is a high-resolution spectrograph operating from the near-ultraviolet to the near-infrared, targeting science cases that include the characterization of exoplanet atmospheres, the search for life bio-signatures, and tests of fundamental physics. To feed the spectrograph with a diffraction-limited beam, ANDES is equipped with a Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) module that relies on a single natural guide star and the M4 itself as the sole deformable mirror, conjugated to the ground layer[8]. Given the stringent performance requirements of ANDES, stable and accurate wavefront correction is essential, making the precise estimation and control of M4 petal modes a critical challenge for the system.

Previous strategies have attempted to mitigate this by defining specific bases. For instance, in the GMT case, the adoption of 7 independent KL bases for each DM segment alongside a set of 7 petal modes was suggested[9]. However, this approach has the drawback that global low-order modes, such as tilt, become a combination of several different modes, which is suboptimal for controlling large wind shake and structural vibrations. Other solutions have included edge actuator coupling, as seen in HARMONI[2], or the use of specific continuous bases[1].

In this work, we seek a robust method to estimate petal modes that remains resilient to the Von Karman turbulent phase. We compare three distinct estimation techniques: a Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) estimator, an estimator based on spatial derivatives, and a neural network-based method.

2. ESTIMATION METHODS

To effectively disentangle the discontinuous petal modes from the continuous atmospheric turbulence, we implemented and tested three different estimators.

2.1 Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) Estimator

The first approach starts from a modal representation (e.g., Zernike or Karhunen-Loève) of the phase mapped into the deformable mirror space. Let Φ be the 1D column vector representing the lexicographically unrolled 2D phase map, and M be the modal basis matrix. The phase is given by:

$$\Phi = Mm, \quad (1)$$

where m is the modal command vector. The matrix M is capable of representing a phase step, piston, or petal mode, yielding:

$$\Phi_{\text{petal}} = Mm_{\text{petal}}. \quad (2)$$

Alternatively, we can define a purely geometric piston representation of the phase using a dedicated piston basis M_{petal} and the piston command vector p :

$$\Phi_{\text{petal}} = M_{\text{petal}}p. \quad (3)$$

By equating the two representations ($Mm_{\text{petal}} = M_{\text{petal}}p$), we can isolate m_{petal} . Assuming M^\dagger is the pseudo-inverse of M , we define a projection matrix P that converts a specific piston command p into its corresponding modal command m_{petal} :

$$P = M^\dagger M_{\text{petal}} \quad (4)$$

$$m_{\text{petal}} = Pp. \quad (5)$$

The core idea of this method is to invert the relationship from the modal commands m back to the pure piston vector p using a Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) estimator, denoted as W_{MMSE} . The estimator relies on the modal covariance matrix C_m , which is derived from the theoretical atmospheric turbulence profile and the chosen modal base, and the a priori piston covariance matrix C_p . We model the latter as:

$$C_p = kC'_p, \quad (6)$$

where C'_p represents the expected covariance of unit-amplitude petal modes and k acts as an empirical free scaling parameter. Ultimately, the piston estimate is computed via:

$$\hat{p} = W_{\text{MMSE}}m, \quad (7)$$

where the linear MMSE reconstructor W_{MMSE} is defined as:

$$W_{\text{MMSE}} = C_p P^T [PC_p P^T + C_m]^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

2.2 Derivatives Estimator

The second estimator operates primarily in the spatial domain. The underlying concept is to filter out the phase step generated by a petal by computing the spatial derivatives of the 2D phase map in the x and y directions, intentionally excluding the edge points (e.g., the spider shadow or the gaps between the mirror segments). The derivatives are given by:

$$d_x(x, y) = \frac{\partial \phi_{2D}(x, y)}{\partial x} \quad (9)$$

$$d_y(x, y) = \frac{\partial \phi_{2D}(x, y)}{\partial y} \quad (10)$$

for any coordinate (x, y) that does not fall on a segment edge.

Since a strict phase step produces a non-zero derivative only at the boundaries between segments, calculating the derivative strictly within the inner area of the segments effectively erases the phase step information. To proceed with the wavefront reconstruction, the 2D derivative maps $d_x(x, y)$ and $d_y(x, y)$ are lexicographically unrolled into 1D column vectors, denoted as d_x and d_y . A continuous, petal-free phase vector $\hat{\Phi}$ can then be reconstructed—similarly to Shack-Hartmann sensor signal processing—using a standard reconstruction matrix R :

$$\hat{\Phi} = R \begin{bmatrix} d_x \\ d_y \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

The petal contribution is then isolated by subtracting this estimated continuous phase from the original unrolled phase vector Φ :

$$\Phi_{\text{petal}} = \Phi - \hat{\Phi}. \quad (12)$$

Finally, this residual is projected to obtain the petal vector estimate \tilde{p} . Since M_{petal} is a rectangular matrix mapping the petal modes to the phase space, we use its Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse M_{petal}^\dagger to compute the final estimate:

$$\tilde{p} = M_{\text{petal}}^\dagger \Phi_{\text{petal}}. \quad (13)$$

2.3 Convolutional Neural Network (U-Net) Estimator

Figure 1. Architecture of the 2D Convolutional U-Net implemented in the SPECULA framework for petal mode estimation.

The third approach employs a 2D Convolutional U-Net architecture[6]. The significant advantage of this data-driven method is its integration into our simulation framework, allowing for continuous online training. Instead of requiring the storage of massive datasets, the network consumes pairs of 2D phase maps and vectors of modal components generated on-the-fly, enabling it to train indefinitely. The training process utilizes an early stopping mechanism triggered when the loss function—a weighted mean squared error that heavily penalizes piston estimation errors compared to other modes—ceases to improve over several epochs.

3. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK AND SETUP

To test and compare these estimators, we utilized SPECULA[10], a next-generation adaptive optics simulation framework. For this preliminary study, we selected a simplified use case consisting of a pupil with only two segments. Consequently, only a single differential piston mode needed to be estimated.

The simulation generated an on-axis source at a wavelength of 750 nm (magnitude 8). The atmosphere was modeled as a random phase with a Von Karman distribution, assuming an outer scale L_0 of 25 m. The simulation ran for a total time of 0.5 seconds with a highly resolved time step of 1 millisecond. A randomly distributed differential piston error was injected into the deformable mirror layer and combined with the continuous atmospheric phase to test the estimators' recovery capabilities.

Figure 2. Truth vs Estimated Differential Piston. The scatter plot compares the estimations from the Derivatives, MMSE, and U-Net methods against the true injected piston, showing near-perfect correlation for all three estimators.

Differential Piston Analysis - Input RMS: 292.989

Figure 3. Differential Piston Analysis for an input RMS of approximately 293 nm. Left: Differential Piston Error vs Time across 500 frames. Right: Error Distribution density histogram for the three estimation methods.

4. RESULTS

We evaluated the performance of the three methods by analyzing the distribution of their estimation errors over the simulated time series. As illustrated in the error distribution analysis, all three implemented methods perform exceptionally well and provide highly correlated estimations of the true injected differential piston.

For an input differential piston with a Root Mean Square (RMS) amplitude of approximately 293 nm, the estimators successfully recovered the petal modes with a small residual error. Specifically, the temporal RMS of the estimation error was:

- 27.9 nm for the Derivatives estimator;
- 33.0 nm for the MMSE estimator;
- 25.2 nm for the Convolutional U-Net.

These results indicate that, in our simplified two-segment test case, the analytical methods (MMSE and Derivatives) provide a robust baseline. Remarkably, the data-driven neural network approach (U-Net) not only

matched but slightly outperformed the precision of the analytical methods, demonstrating its strong potential and high adaptability for non-linear wavefront reconstruction regimes without requiring extensive offline datasets.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Controlling petal modes is essential for the optimal functioning of segmented adaptive optics systems like those planned for the ELT. Our comparative study shows that differential piston estimation robust to atmospheric turbulence can be successfully achieved using analytical techniques (MMSE and edge-blind derivatives) as well as modern deep learning architectures (U-Net). Now that this robust setup is established within the SPECULA framework, we are prepared to further investigate the estimation of petal modes in more complex and realistic scenarios, specifically focusing on the full multi-segment pupils and modal bases of actual telescopes, including the ELT's M4.

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